

Effect of Digital Financial Services on the Operational Efficiency of SMEs in South-West Nigeria

Adeyombo Gbenga ADEGUNJU¹, Ayoola Abimbola ESO², Kolawole Fatai BISIRIYU³ and Godwin Emmanuel OYEDOKUN⁴

¹Department of Management and Accounting, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria, adeyombo.adegunju@gmail.com || +234 803 563 6175

²Department of Finance, Lagos State University of Science and Technology, Lagos, Nigeria ayoeso@hotmail.com; +234 802 291 3114

³Assistant Director Tax, Large Taxpayer Audit Department, Federal Inland Revenue Service, Lagos, Nigeria, +2348033670220; kolawole.kb@gmail.com; bisiriyu.kolawole@firs.gov.ng

⁴Professor, Department of Management and Accounting, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria, godwinoye@yahoo.com || +234 803 373 7184, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8317-3924>

Abstract

Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) play a vital role in the overall economic performance of the country by diversifying the economy, creating jobs, fostering innovation, and distributing wealth. These enterprises encountered various obstacles which affect their survival and growth opportunities and their contribution to economic growth. This study investigated the impact of digital financial services on the operational efficiency of SMEs in South-west Nigeria. The study employed mixed-methods research design. The population comprised of 149,317 SMEs in South-west Nigeria. Using stratified random sampling and purposive sampling techniques 399 respondents were selected from the total population. Data was gathered using a structured questionnaire with close-ended questions and a focus group discussion and were statistically analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21.0 and descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings revealed that digital financial services played a significant role in enhancing operational efficiency of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Southwest Nigeria. The analysis of digital financial services showed a weak positive correlation with operational efficiency, explaining only 5.8% of the variation in operational costs. The study concluded that digital financial services has impacted SMEs operational efficiency positively. The study therefore recommended that government and financial institutions invest in infrastructure that expands internet connectivity and mobile platform accessibility, especially in rural regions, to promote greater digital financial inclusion, enhancing digital infrastructure, and making financial products more accessible so as to empower SMEs and thereby drive sustainable growth.

Keywords: Digital financial Services, Operational efficiency, Nigeria, Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), South-west

Word Count: 241

Introduction

Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria contributes to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and workforce. SMEs performance has a considerable impact on the overall economic performance of the country (Erhunmwunse, 2024). These enterprises play a crucial role in diversifying the economy, creating jobs, fostering innovation, and distributing wealth. Nevertheless, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) encounter obstacles such as insufficient funding, deficient record keeping, difficulty distinguishing between company and personal capital, lack of infrastructure, and inadequate skills. Survival and growth opportunities encompass factors such as job creation, ease of setting up businesses, contribution to GDP, and possibility for further expansion. Despite the considerable prospects presented by the country's large population and rising consumer market, these variables result in increased costs and decreased profitability (Poi & Lebura, 2021).

The concerning frequency of Nigerian Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) experiencing failure prior to their fifth anniversary has been emphasised. This study highlighted that tough economic conditions, restricted access to capital, and inadequate business practices are the main factors that hinder growth and transformation. Approximately 80 percent of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) encounter substantial difficulties, largely as a result of the imposition of several taxes. This load has a detrimental effect on businesses throughout the country (Joseph, 2023). The Nigerian government has introduced policies and programmes to promote the flow of financial services to small and medium-sized organisations. However, these efforts have not resulted in substantial growth and development for small-scale businesses due to many obstacles that are limiting their progress.

The devaluation of the Nigerian naira has significantly impacted the operations of small and medium-sized businesses, increasing import expenses, inflation, and financial instability. This has negatively impacted on profit margins, operational costs, and price competitiveness. However, SMEs selling internationally could capitalise on the decrease in currency value, potentially increasing export earnings. Strict monetary policies and reduced purchasing power may result in higher financing costs, further intensifying financial uncertainty and postponing investments. Ensuring access to financial services plays a vital role in promoting broad-based economic development and reducing poverty, employment generation, wealth accumulation, and individual well-being (Oke, Soetan & Ayedun, 2023). Financial inclusion in Nigeria is crucial for enabling accessible fiscal tools and assistance available to individuals and organisations. However, SMEs face challenges in securing financing due to limited access to credit facilities. Financial inclusion initiatives should focus on enhancing financial literacy among SMEs, enabling them to understand and evaluate financial solutions. Banks struggle to meet the significant costs associated with lending to SMEs due to insufficient capital reserves, inadequate financial documentation, and intense market competition (Oyedokun & Amoo, 2023).

This study aims to examine the factors influencing the operational efficiency of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. It places particular emphasis on how adoption of digital financial services with the objective to offer policy-driven recommendations that promote financial integration and reduce the adverse effects of factors influencing the operational efficiency on SME performance, with a particular focus on Oyo State and the broader Nigerian context.

Literature Review

Financial Inclusion among SMEs

Financial inclusion traditionally means ensuring that individuals can access and effectively use a broad range of affordable and convenient financial services. Such access and usage are widely acknowledged as vital drivers of economic growth and development (Nwanko & Nwanko, 2021). Financial inclusion involves providing lasting, suitable, affordable, and effective financial services to underserved groups, especially those in rural regions. It also relates to the range, quality, and ease of access to financial products and services for individuals who are either excluded from or have limited access to formal financial institutions (World Bank, 2022).

Financial inclusion has also been defined as a condition in which everyone capable of utilising financial services is able to access a full range of high-quality financial products that are affordable, delivered with respect, and offered in a convenient manner. It plays a vital role in helping individuals expand or diversify their household income, improve cash flow, and build resilience during times of hardship. By enabling asset accumulation, financial inclusion allows people to manage unexpected financial challenges through consumption smoothing, thereby preventing the need to sell productive assets in times of crisis (Clark, 2021).

Financial inclusion refers to a condition where both individuals and businesses can obtain financial products and services should be affordable, relevant, and provided in a responsible and sustainable manner. These offerings encompass payments, transactions, investments, credit, borrowing, savings,

and insurance. Numerous countries have already enacted a variety of policies and reforms aimed at boosting financial inclusion for SMEs. These measures often involve direct interventions to increase bank lending, including state-owned banks dedicated to SMEs, credit guarantee programs, and regulations governing interest rates. Financial inclusion of SMEs is central to addressing economic diversification and growth challenges faced by many nations. Given that SMEs constitute a significant portion of businesses in many regions, limited access to finance remains a major obstacle in numerous countries (Taiwo, Falohun, & Agwu, 2017).

Small and Medium Scale Enterprise Performance

The effectiveness of SMEs covers three primary dimensions of business outcomes: financial results (including earnings, asset returns, and investment yields), market-related performance (such as sales volume and market penetration), and shareholder gains (evaluated through overall shareholder returns and value created economically). This pertains to the measurable achievements or effects of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) assessed in relation to their planned targets and aims. SME effectiveness involves defining expected results, formulating approaches to accomplish those targets, implementing strategies, and evaluating whether the goals have been fulfilled (Goldberg & Knetter, 2017).

Financial inclusion directly or indirectly on performance of SMEs

Financial inclusion (FI) is the process by which individuals and businesses, irrespective of their income, gain access to and can effectively utilise the financial services necessary to improve their quality of life (World Bank, 2018). Financial inclusion described a situation where individuals can access a full spectrum of financial services affordably, conveniently, and with dignity and respect (Center for Financial Inclusion, 2018). These services should be provided to consumers in a responsible, secure, and sustainable manner within an appropriately regulated environment (Dogarawa, 2017).

At the macroeconomic level, financial inclusion contributed to a broader deposit base, which strengthens the financial system and enhances its stability (Aguera, 2021). The IMF stated that constraints arising from various macroeconomic factors, such as stability, equity, and economic growth, affect the extent of financial inclusion at the national scale (Sahay et al., 2021).

Advancements in information and communication technology have greatly enhanced digital financing. Governments, development agencies, and service providers have increasingly prioritised delivering financial services through digital platforms as a progressive move toward achieving greater financial inclusion (Vo & Shang, 2019). Services such as mobile banking have made it easier for financially excluded individuals to transfer money electronically. This approach helps reduce the risks of loss, theft, and financial crimes linked to cash handling. For those facing economic and social disadvantages, digital finance offers a more advantageous alternative (Vasani, Selvam, & Selvam, 2019). Efforts to promote financial inclusion will focus on overcoming challenges related to credit access, which often hinder SME growth. The Financial Inclusion Alliance (FIA, 2018) highlights that the use of smartphones and broadband Internet is becoming increasingly important in enabling access to secure and affordable financial services such as money transfers, credit, savings, and both domestic and international payments.

Mobile technologies have introduced a significant transformation in the financial system. The development and adoption of digital innovations through collaborative efforts can accelerate the delivery of financial services, advancing financial inclusion (Dorfleitner & Roble, 2018). Enhanced financial inclusion drives and enables increased savings, easier access to payment systems, and the widespread use of smartphones and ATMs (Dorfleitner & Roble, 2018). Sustainable economic growth depends on a large segment of the population having access to formal financial services. Increased financial inclusion is associated with greater investment, more job opportunities, higher incomes, and reduced poverty (Moghalu, 2022). To improve financial inclusion for the broader population, especially those in rural areas, financial service providers must lower operating account fees (Moghalu, 2022). Formal financial institutions aiming to sustainably deliver adequate and efficient services to rural populations face significant challenges due to high transaction costs in sparsely populated areas and rigid, complex methods for assessing clients' risk profiles. Addressing ICT-related issues especially concerning cash transfers, cost of capital, utilisation, and access to finance will be vital for the growth and development of SMEs.

Operational Cost

Operational costs are essential expenditures incurred by a firm on a day-to-day basis, which are not directly associated with output. The expenses include remuneration, compensation, lease payments, utility bills, and other operational expenditures. These expenses have a substantial effect on the company's profitability since they directly influence its financial well-being. Rising operational expenses often results in a decline in profitability, but cutting costs may improve profit margins. This emphasised the significance of effective management of operating costs in order to maintain and enhance profitability in the manufacturing sector. Operational costs may be classified into many categories, including administrative expenditures, rent and utilities, maintenance and repairs, insurance and taxes, and depreciation and amortisation. Administrative costs include the remuneration for administrative workers, the procurement of office supplies, and several other basic company expenditures. The expenses for rent and utilities include the costs associated with leasing office space as well as the fees for utilities such as electricity, water, and other such services. Regular maintenance and repairs are essential for ensuring efficient operations. Insurance and taxes are components of operating expenses. Depreciation and amortisation are accounting measures that reflect the decrease in value of tangible and intangible assets as time passes, even though no actual cash is involved.

Efficiently managing operational costs entails maximising these expenses while maintaining the company's operational quality and efficiency (Istan et al, 2021). Efficient cost management is essential for maintaining competitive pricing and sustaining profitability. Managing operational expenses is essential for minimising mistakes in service handling and ensuring precise financial reporting, which is crucial for strategic planning and decision-making. An effective operational cost accounting information system enhances internal control over operational expenses by assuring precise recording and reporting of financial transactions, facilitating efficient monitoring and control. Cost accounting information systems may effectively manage and control expenses, providing precise financial information, facilitating strategic decision-making, and improving internal control mechanisms. By comprehending and using these principles, organisations may enhance their operational effectiveness and attain their financial goals (Yeni, Komara, Susanto, & Rusjiana, 2023).

Theoretical Review

This study is anchored on Financial Inclusion Theory. The concept of financial inclusion has been developed and advocated by several researchers and international organisations over the years. Thorsten Beck, a well-known advocate of this idea, has conducted considerable research that emphasised the significance of financial development and inclusion in promoting economic growth and alleviating

poverty. Beck, together with other researchers such as Asli Demirgüç-Kunt and Patrick Honohan, has established the foundation for comprehending the ways in which having access to financial services may enhance the capabilities of people and organisations, resulting in wider economic advantages (Beck & Demirgüç-Kunt, 2008).

According to Beck and Demirgüç-Kunt (2008), the notion of financial inclusion is based on three fundamental assumptions. Firstly, it presupposes that having access to a diverse array of financial services, such as savings, credit, insurance, and payment services, empowers people and enterprises to enhance their financial welfare. This access facilitates the process of consuming goods and services, mitigating risks, and capitalising on development prospects. Furthermore, the idea posits that financial services have to be accessible at a reasonable cost, easy in terms of availability, and customised to cater to the requirements of various populations, particularly those who are underserved and disadvantaged. Moreover, it assumes that having a strong understanding of financial concepts and principles is essential, as it enables individuals to make well-informed choices about financial goods and services. According to the idea, it is crucial to have a regulatory and institutional framework that supports and promotes an inclusive financial system. This framework should aim to safeguard consumers and maintain the stability of financial institutions (Beck & Demirgüç-Kunt, 2008).

Cull, Demirgüç-Kunt, and Morduch (2014) argued that a lack of sufficient knowledge and assistance in financial matters may result in the improper use of financial goods, which in turn can lead to excessive debt and financial hardship. Furthermore, there is apprehension that financial inclusion programs may concentrate quantity over quality, placing emphasis on the amount of newly established accounts rather than guaranteeing that these accounts are actively used and advantageous. Another critique is that the emphasis on digital financial services as a method to attain financial inclusion may exclude those who do not have access to technology or lack the necessary technical skills to use these services proficiently. The presence of a digital gap may worsen pre-existing disparities, especially in areas where access to the internet and mobile phones is restricted (Donovan, 2012). In addition, the fast growth of digital financial services gives rise to apprehensions about data privacy and cyber security, as an increasing number of individuals and enterprises become susceptible to digital fraud and identity theft. Some opponents contend that financial inclusion initiatives should be complemented by more extensive economic and social changes. Financial inclusion alone may not be enough to promote long-term economic growth without also addressing essential concerns such as education, healthcare, and infrastructure (Collins, Morduch, Rutherford, & Ruthven, 2009). Critics argue in favor of a comprehensive strategy that combines financial inclusion with other development measures in order to create a fairer and more equal economy.

Despite the objections, the notion of financial inclusion has been extensively implemented in both policy-making and practical applications, resulting in a substantial influence on the global financial environment. Implementing the financial inclusion principle will provide improved accessibility to vital financial services for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Southwest Nigeria, hence fostering their growth and prosperity. Using financial instruments such as microloans, savings accounts, and insurance, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) may effectively mitigate risks, allocate funds towards productive assets, and enhance their overall financial well-being.

Empirical Review

Rasheed, Siddiqui, Mahmood and Khan, (2019) investigated the role of digital micro-financial services in enhancing financial inclusion for Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Pakistan. The study focused on the difficulties SMEs have getting financing since banks are reluctant to provide them with loans. By a thorough analysis of the body of current literature and secondary data. The results demonstrated that, in comparison to conventional cash handling techniques, digital micro financial services have greatly enhanced the financial management capacities of SMEs in Pakistan. These services allow businesses to handle transactions more effectively, save expenses, and increase security.

More SMEs are now able to access formal financial systems because to the growth of digital financial services, which has also promoted broader financial inclusion. The survey does, however, also point out a number of obstacles that prevent SMEs from using digital financial services widely. These include low levels of technology knowledge and financial literacy among SMEs, poor infrastructure, expensive transaction fees, and security concerns. The results indicate that while there has been a notable advancement in the promotion of digital financial inclusion, more focused initiatives are necessary to fully achieve the potential advantages for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and the wider economy. In emerging nations like Pakistan, promoting a more accessible financial market via digital micro financial services may be very important for accelerating economic development and lowering poverty.

Kambi and Onyiego (2022) investigated the influence of digital financial inclusion strategies on the financial expansion of Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Enterprises (MSMEs) in Kenya. The study focused on mobile phone banking, electronic money banking, agency banking, and digital banking applications as the four main pillars of digital financial inclusion. It looks at how they affect the financial development of MSMEs over a five-year span (2016-2020). Using secondary data from the Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS), Central Bank of Kenya (CBK), and FinAccess Business Survey, the research uses a descriptive survey and inferential statistics technique. Data on MSMEs' financial performance from 2016 to 2020 was examined in the research. The data were summarised using descriptive statistics, and the significance of the independent variables (mobile banking, electronic banking, agency banking, and banking apps) with respect to the dependent variable (financial growth of MSMEs) was tested using inferential statistics, such as regression analysis. The results demonstrate that the financial expansion of MSMEs in Kenya is favourably impacted by all four of the components of digital financial inclusion, with mobile phone banking having the greatest influence. The report suggests that in order to further help MSMEs' growth and Kenya's economic development, governments should encourage and improve digital financial services. It is recommended that future studies examine other financial inclusion-related issues and how they affect MSMEs.

Gosal and Nainggolan (2023) explored the influence of digital financial literacy on Indonesian smes' financial behaviour and financial well-being, with particular emphasis on the function of digital financial literacy (DFL) in the modern business environment. Business operations have undergone a fast digital change, which highlights the need for SMEs to negotiate digital financial landscapes in order to improve their financial stability and development potential. The study expands on earlier research by emphasising the role that digital financial literacy plays in supporting SMEs' financial well-being. The research looked at SMEs in Medan, Surabaya, Makassar, and Bali, four important cities, and offered a thorough review of the existing level of digital financial literacy among SME owners. In order to objectively assess SMEs' financial performance, the quantitative approach used online questionnaires to gather information from 186 respondents, confirming that the businesses had been in existence for more than a year. The study utilised the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) approach to examine the relationships between variables and test the hypotheses. The results show a strong correlation between SMEs' financial well-being and their financial behaviour when it comes to digital financial literacy. The improvement of financial behaviour is greatly impacted by digital financial literacy, and this has a major influence on SMEs' financial well-being. The favourable impacts of DFL on financial outcomes are amplified by financial behaviour, which acts as a mediator between digital financial literacy and financial well-being. These results have significant ramifications for stakeholders in SMEs, financial institutions, and regulators. In order to enable SMEs to successfully use digital financial instruments, the report emphasises the necessity for focused education and training initiatives to increase digital financial literacy.

Sulqarnain, Mustehsan, Balouch, and Munir, (2023) investigated the influence of digital finance and financial inclusion on SMEs Performance looking at the role of technological adaptation and how these two factors affect the ways in which small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) in Pakistan perform. SME access to financial services is often severely hampered, even though SMEs are essential for economic expansion, employment generation, and poverty reduction. The goal of the study is to

comprehend how these variables affect SME performance and how these interactions are mediated by technological adaptability. Utilising a quantitative research approach, 212 SMEs in Pakistan were given surveys as part of the study. After conducting a pilot study to improve the survey instrument, the main online survey was used to gather data. SPSS was used for statistical analysis, while Hayes's process macro was used for moderation analysis. The results demonstrate the beneficial effects of digital finance and financial inclusion on SME success. Compared to their less adaptable peers, SMEs who embrace technological adaptation gain more from digital banking and financial inclusion. SMEs with better access to financial services perform better, and there is a favourable association between financial inclusion and SMEs' productivity, according to key results. The success of SMEs is associated with digital finance since it makes financing more accessible and reduces transaction costs. The link between digital finance, SME performance, and financial inclusion is moderated by technological adaptability. SMEs that are more adept at adjusting to new technology stand to gain more from digital finance and financial inclusion. According to the study's findings, digital finance and financial inclusion are essential for improving SME performance, especially when SMEs are flexible enough to adopt new technology. To encourage the expansion of SMEs, policymakers and financial institutions should prioritise expanding access to financial services and promoting the use of digital technology.

Methodology

The study employed mixed-method research design, The population of this study comprised of 149,317 SMEs in South-west Nigeria. Taro Yamane (1967) statistical formula was used to determine sample size while stratified random sampling and purposive sampling techniques were employed to select 399 SME owners from the total population. Data was gathered using a structured questionnaire with close-ended questions and a focus group discussion. Data were statistically analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21.0 with descriptive and inferential statistics.

Result and Presentation of Data

Table 1: Demographic Variables of the Respondents

SN	Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Age		
	Under 25	9	3.3
	25-34	100	36.6
	35-44	103	37.7
	45-54	19	7.0
	55-64	30	11.0
	65 and above	12	4.4
	Total	273	100
2	Gender		
	Male	179	65.6
	Female	94	34.4
	Total	273	100
3	Education Background		
	No Formal Education	13	4.8
	Primary	40	14.7
	Secondary	88	32.2
	First Degree	132	48.4
	Total	273	100
4	Number of Employees		

	1.-10	245	89.7
	11-20	14	5.1
	21-30	9	3.3
	41-50	5	1.8
	Total	273	100
5	Years in Operation		
	1-5 years	135	49.5
	6-9 years	22	8.1
	10 years and above	66	24.2
	5	50	18.3
	Total	273	100
6	Industry Sector		
	Agriculture	19	7.0
	Manufacturing	43	15.8
	Retail/Wholesale	129	47.3
	Services	36	13.2
	Information Technology	28	10.3
	Healthcare	18	6.6
	Total	273	100
7	Ownership Structure		
	Sole Proprietorship	216	79.1
	Partnership	30	11.0
	limited Liability Company	27	9.9
	Total	273	100
8	Family Business		
	Yes	18	6.6
	No	255	93.4
	Total	273	100
9	Business Training and Development		
	No	252	92.3
	Yes	21	7.7
	Total	273	100

Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 revealed the distribution of demographic variables of the respondents. The age distribution of SME operators in Southwest Nigeria shows that the majority are within the productive working-age bracket. Most respondents are between 35–44 years (37.7%) and 25–34 years (36.6%), indicating that SME activities are predominantly driven by young to middle-aged adults. A smaller proportion of respondents are either under 25 (3.3%) or above 65 (4.4%), suggesting limited participation of the very young or elderly in small and medium-scale enterprise ownership. Gender-wise, the data reveals a male-dominated SME landscape, with 65.6% of respondents being male and 34.4% female. While women represent over one-third of the total respondents, the gap points to potential gender-related barriers in accessing resources, financial services, or entrepreneurial opportunities. This calls for targeted policies to enhance female participation in the SME sector.

The educational background of the respondents indicated a relatively high level of formal education among SME operators. A majority of 48.4% hold a first degree, while 32.2% have completed secondary education. Only a small fraction of respondents (4.8%) has no formal education. This suggests that

education plays a significant role in entrepreneurial engagement, likely influencing business decisions, financial literacy, and adaptation to market fluctuations. In terms of business size, the overwhelming majority of respondents (89.7%) operate micro-enterprises employing between 1 to 10 people. Very few have scaled beyond 20 employees, reflecting the limited growth and expansion of SMEs in the region. This points to the need for better support systems to help businesses scale up sustainably.

Regarding years in operation, 49.5% of the businesses have been operating for 1–5 years, indicating a high level of new or recently established ventures. 24.2% have survived beyond 10 years, showing some degree of longevity and stability. However, the entry "5 = 50 = 18.3%" appears inconsistent and may require clarification, possibly being a data entry error related to years in operation. The industry distribution shows that Retail and Wholesale trade dominates (47.3%), followed by Manufacturing (15.8%) and Services (13.2%). Other sectors like Agriculture (7.0%), Information Technology (10.3%), and Healthcare (6.6%) have lower representation. This indicates a concentration of SMEs in trade-related activities, while more capital- or skill-intensive sectors are less explored.

Ownership structure analysis reveals that 79.1% of businesses are sole proprietorships, signifying that most SME owners prefer individual ownership. Only 11.0% operate as partnerships, and 9.9% as limited liability companies, highlighting limited formalisation in business structure. This could affect access to funding, risk-sharing, and long-term sustainability. When asked about family business involvement, only 6.6% of respondents affirmed that their enterprises were family-run, whereas 93.4% indicated otherwise. This suggested that most SMEs in the region are not family businesses but are likely founded and run by individual entrepreneurs. Lastly, the data shows a significant gap in capacity development, as 92.3% of respondents have not received any form of business training or development, with only 7.7% indicating they had. This highlighted a crucial area for intervention, as training and development are essential for improving business practices, adaptability to economic shifts like exchange rate fluctuations, and overall SME performance.

Analysis of Research Question

What is the effect of digital financial services on the operational efficiency of SMEs?

Table 2: Digital Financial Services and Operational Efficiency of SMEs

		SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)
1	Does your business use mobile banking	54 (19.8%)	42 (15.4%)	0 (0%)	105 (38.5%)	72 (26.4%)
2	Have you adopted digital payment systems in your business operations	0 (0%)	32 (11.7%)	0 (0%)	88 (32.2%)	153 (56.0%)
3	How accessible are online financial services to your business	Not Accessible (%)	Slightly Accessible (%)	Moderate (%)	Highly Accessible (%)	Very Highly Accessible (%)
		48 (17.6%)	59 (21.6%)	32 (11.7%)	57 (20.9%)	77 (28.2%)
		No Impact (%)	Low Impact (%)	Moderate Impact (%)	High Impact (%)	Very High Impact (%)

4	How has the use of digital financial services affected your operational costs	4 (1.5%)	0 (0%)	14 (5.1%)	102 (37.4%)	153 (56.0%)
---	---	----------	--------	-----------	-------------	-------------

Researcher’s Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 revealed that digital financial tools, such as mobile banking and digital payment systems—are increasingly being adopted by small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Southwest Nigeria, and they play a significant role in enhancing operational efficiency. The adoption of mobile banking is growing among SMEs, with a majority of respondents confirming its use. Specifically, 38.5% agreed and 26.4% strongly agreed that their businesses utilise mobile banking services. However, a notable 19.8% strongly disagreed and 15.4% disagreed, showing that while uptake is significant, a portion of SMEs are still not leveraging mobile banking. This may be due to digital literacy gaps, infrastructure limitations, or trust issues in online transactions. Regarding the adoption of digital payment systems, the trend is even more positive. A combined 88.2% of respondents confirmed adoption, with 56.0% strongly agreeing and 32.2% agreeing that they use digital payments in their business operations. Only 11.7% disagreed, and none were neutral or strongly disagreed. This high adoption rate reflects a shift toward cashless transactions and improved ease of payments for both businesses and their customers.

The accessibility of online financial services, such as internet banking, mobile apps, and e-wallets, showed a balanced spread. While 28.2% described these services as “very highly accessible” and 20.9% as “highly accessible,” others found them less reachable—17.6% said “not accessible” and 21.6% said “slightly accessible.” This indicated some progress in digital inclusion but also highlighted ongoing challenges in internet access, digital infrastructure, or service coverage. The impact of digital financial services on operational costs is very positive. A combined 93.4% of respondents stated that digital services have a “high” (37.4%) or “very high” (56.0%) impact on reducing operational expenses. Only 1.5% felt there was no impact, and 5.1% reported a moderate impact, underscoring the cost-saving benefits of going digital—such as reduced cash handling, faster transaction times, and lower administrative costs. In summary, digital financial services have significantly improved the operational efficiency of SMEs in Southwest Nigeria. Through mobile banking and digital payment systems, businesses are reducing costs, streamlining transactions, and improving customer convenience. However, challenges remain in ensuring equal accessibility and addressing digital literacy or infrastructure barriers to enable more inclusive digital adoption across the SME sector.

Hypothesis Testing

H01: Digital financial services significantly improve the operational efficiency of SMEs.

Table 3: Relationship between Digital Financial Services and Operational Efficiency of SMEs was Analysed Using Linear Regression

Model Summary

Model	R	R Squared	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.241 ^a	.058	.055	.707	.058	16.734	1	27	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Digital Financial Services

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8.370	1	8.370	16.734	.000 ^b
	Residual	135.549	271	.500		
	Total	143.919	272			

a. Dependent Variable: Operational Costs; b. Predictors: (Constant), Digital Financial Services

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.257	.298		10.915	.000
	Digital Financial Services	.079	.019	.241	4.091	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Operational Costs

The analysis examined the relationship between Digital Financial Services and Operational Costs through a linear regression model. The model showed that there is a weak positive correlation between these two variables, with an R value of 0.241. This indicates that while Digital Financial Services has an effect on operational costs, the strength of the relationship is relatively low. The R Square value of 0.058 further supported this, showing that only 5.8% of the variation in operational costs can be explained by the use of Digital Financial Services. This suggested that while Digital Financial Services contribute to operational costs, they do not account for a substantial portion of the variation in these costs. The Adjusted R Square value of 0.055 is slightly lower, reflecting a small decrease in explanatory power when accounting for the number of predictors.

The standard error of the estimate is 0.707, which reflected the variability of the data that the model has not been able to explain. While this value is relatively moderate, it indicated that there is still some error in the model's predictions. The Change Statistics revealed that the inclusion of Digital Financial Services in the model explained an additional 5.8% of the variation in operational costs. The F statistic of 16.734 are highly significant, and the corresponding p-value of 0.000 showed that the overall model is statistically significant, confirming that Digital Financial Services do have a measurable impact on operational costs. The ANOVA table also provided insight into the significance of the model. The regression sum of squares is 8.370, which represents the variation explained by the model, while the residual sum of squares (135.549) represents the unexplained variation. The high F value (16.734) confirms that the model is statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.000 reinforcing this conclusion.

Looking at the coefficients, the constant value of 3.257 represents the expected operational cost when Digital Financial Services have no impact. The coefficient for Digital Financial Services is 0.079, meaning that for each unit increase in the use of Digital Financial Services, operational costs increase by 0.079 units. The standardised coefficient (Beta) of 0.241 suggested a moderate impact of Digital Financial Services on operational costs compared to other factors. The t-value of 4.091 indicates that this relationship is statistically significant, as the value is well above the typical threshold of 2. The p-value of 0.000 further confirms the significance of this coefficient. In conclusion, the results of the analysis confirm that Digital Financial Services have a statistically significant positive relationship with Operational Costs. For each increase in the use of Digital Financial Services, operational costs rise. However, the low R Square value of 0.058 indicates that Digital Financial Services explain only a small proportion of the variability in operational costs, suggesting that other factors not included in the model

contribute significantly to operational costs. Despite this, the relationship observed is statistically significant and meaningful.

The descriptive analysis provided offers a detailed examination of the adoption and impact of digital financial tools such as mobile banking and digital payment systems on the operational efficiency of SMEs in Southwest Nigeria. These findings can be related to the ANOVA and regression results discussed earlier, which examined the relationship between Digital Financial Services and Operational Costs. Both the descriptive analysis and the regression results converge on the idea that digital financial services are having a significant, but not overwhelming, effect on the operational costs of SMEs in Southwest Nigeria. The high adoption rates of digital payment systems and mobile banking indicate that SMEs are embracing these tools to enhance efficiency, reduce costs, and improve customer convenience. However, the modest R Square value from the regression model suggested that other factors such as digital literacy, infrastructure, and financial products tailored to SMEs also played a crucial role in determining the overall impact on operational costs.

Discussion of Findings

The analysis of digital financial services revealed a weak positive correlation with operational efficiency, explaining only 5.8% of the variation in operational costs. Despite this, digital tools like mobile banking and digital payment systems do contribute to SME efficiency, especially in adaptable environments, though their effectiveness is limited by high transaction fees, infrastructure challenges, and low digital literacy (Kambi & Onyiego, 2022). Digital financial services, although providing opportunities for SME efficiency, were identified in the IDIs as being limited by concerns over cybersecurity, data privacy, and low digital literacy. The study confirmed these challenges, revealing a weak positive correlation (explaining only 5.8% of the variation in operational costs) between digital financial services and operational efficiency. While digital tools like mobile banking and digital payment systems have shown some positive impact on SME efficiency, the effectiveness of these tools is hampered by high transaction fees, infrastructure limitations, and the digital literacy gap. These findings are in line with the IDI responses, where the lack of trust in digital financial platforms and the vulnerability to cyber threats were key concerns for SMEs. Moreover, the study highlighted that while digital financial services can enhance financial management and broaden financial inclusion, these services need to be supported by better infrastructure and higher digital literacy to realise their full potential.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, the findings of this study underscore the profound influence of digital financial services on the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Southwest Nigeria. Digital financial tools play pivotal roles in shaping the operational efficiency, investment decisions, and overall growth trajectories of SMEs. However, the challenges of digital literacy gaps, and financial product awareness, indicated the need for targeted interventions. The study revealed that improving financial literacy, enhancing digital infrastructure, and making financial products more accessible are key to empowering SMEs and driving sustainable growth.

To effectively support SMEs, it is essential for stakeholders, including policymakers, financial institutions, and development agencies, to focus on creating an enabling environment that addresses both the financial and non-financial barriers limiting SME growth. By fostering a more inclusive and supportive financial ecosystem, SMEs will be better positioned to thrive in an increasingly volatile economic landscape.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were offered:

1. **Strengthen Financial Literacy Among SME Stakeholders:** To maximise the benefits of digital financial services, it is essential to implement continuous financial literacy programs tailored to the needs of SME owners and their employees. These programs

should focus on enhancing their understanding of financial management, investment planning, and the effective use of digital financial tools. Empowering SMEs with this knowledge will improve their ability to make informed financial decisions, manage risks, and drive sustainable growth.

2. Expand Digital Infrastructure for Broader Access: Improving digital access remains a critical step toward inclusive financial participation. The government, in collaboration with financial institutions and the private sector, should prioritise investments in digital infrastructure, especially in rural areas. Enhancing internet connectivity and mobile platform accessibility will enable more SMEs to adopt digital financial services, thereby improving their operational efficiency and market reach.
3. Promote Macroeconomic Stability to Support SME Growth: Stable economic policies are crucial for the resilience of SMEs. The government should focus on stabilising the exchange rate and fostering broader economic stability. This would help ease the financial burdens faced by SMEs, particularly those that rely on imported goods or raw materials and create a more predictable environment for business operations and planning.

References

- Aguera, P. (2021). Financial inclusion, growth and poverty reduction. ECAAS Regional Conference. Brassavile.
- Beck, T. & Demirgüç-Kunt, A. (2008). Access to finance: an unfinished agenda. *The World Bank Economic Review*, 22(3), 383-396.
- Center for Financial Inclusion – CFI (2018). CFI's vision of financial inclusion. Retrieved from <http://www.centerforfinancialinclusion.org/our-definition-of-financial-inclusion>
- Clark, H. Financial inclusion and HIV/AIDS: Some issues for consideration for the workshop on Micro-finance and HIV/AIDS. *Journal of Parker*, 2(3), 23-26.
- Collins, D., Morduch, J., Rutherford, S. & Ruthven, O. *Portfolios of the Poor: How the World's Poor Live on \$2 a Day*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 2009.
- Cull, R., Demirgüç-Kunt, A. & Morduch, J. (2014). Financial inclusion and development: recent impact evidence. World Bank Policy Research Working Paper no. 7136.
- Dogarawa, A.B. (2017). Bank recapitalisation and funds availability to small and medium enterprises in Nigeria. *Journal of Business and Management* 7(4), 23-26.
- Donovan, K. (2012). *Mobile Money for Financial Inclusion*. In *Information and Communications for Development 2012: Maximising Mobile*, ed. Kelly, T. & Rossotto, C. Washington, DC: World Bank, 61-73
- Dorfleitner, G. & Roble, The financial performance of the health care industry: A global regional and industry specific empirical investigation. *European Journal of Health Economics*, 19(4), 585–594.
- Erhunmwunse. K. (2024). Analysis of factors affecting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMES) access to finance in Edo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities Social Science and Management (IJHSSM)*, 4(2), 1432-1441.
- Goldberg, L. S. & Knetter, M. M. (2017). The effects of currency rate changes on US manufacturing: Evidence from Microdata. *Journal of Political Economy*, 125(4), 1171-1216. World Bank,

- Financial Sector Assessment: Financial Sector Assessment Program* Washington D.C: World Bank, 2018.
- Gosal, G. G. & Nainggolan, R. (2023). The influence of digital financial literacy on Indonesian smes' financial behavior and financial well-being. *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 8(12), 1-13.
- Istan, M., Husainah, N., Istan, M., Suganda, A. D. Siswanti, I. & Fahlevi, M. (2021). The effects of production and operational costs, capital structure and company growth on the profitability: Evidence from manufacturing industry. *Accounting*, 7, 1725-1730.
- Joseph, B. (2023). *80% of SMEs fails in Nigeria Due to Economic Challenges and Regulatory Constraints- Report. MSME Africa*. Retrieved from https://msmeafricaonline.com/80-of-smes-fails-in-nigeria-due-to-economic-challenges-and-regulatory-constraints-report/#google_vignette
- Moghalu, K. C. (2022). The challenge of financial inclusion: The Nigerian perspective, text of remarks at the 2022 global policy forum of the Alliance for Financial Inclusion (AFI) at Riviera Maya, Mexico on September 28, 2022.
- Kambi, E. N. & Onyiego, G. (2022). Effects of digital financial inclusion on financial growth of micro, small & medium enterprises in Kenya. *The Strategic Journal of Business & Change Management*, 9(4), 476-493.
- Nwanko, O. Nwanko, N. O. (2021). Sustainability of financial inclusion to rural dwellers in Nigeria: Problems and way forward. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 5(5), 24-31.
- Oke, D.F. Soetan, R.O. & Ayedun. T. A. (2023). Financial inclusion and the performance of micro, small and medium enterprises in southwest Nigeria. 29th RSEP International Conference on Economics, Finance & Business 1-2 February 2023, HCC. ST. MORITS HOTEL, Barcelona, Spain, 39-50.
- Oyedokun, G. E. & Amoo, A. A. (2023). Financial inclusion and performance of the small and medium enterprises in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Social Science and Management Technology*, 5(6), 184-186.
- Poi, G. & Lebura, S. (2021). Challenges and prospects for small and medium scale enterprises (smes) in the post-pandemic Nigerian economy. *International Journal of Business Management*, 04(12), 53-64.
- Rasheed, R., Siddiqui, S. H., Mahmood, I. & Khan, S. N. (2019). Financial inclusion for SMEs: role of digital micro-financial services. *Review of Economics and Development Studies*, 5(3), 571-580.
- Sahay et al., R. (2021). Financial Inclusion: Can It Meet Multiple Macroeconomic Goals? IMF Staff Discussion Note 15/17.
- Taiwo, J. N., Falohun, T.O. & Agwu, M. E. (2017). SMEs financing and its effects on Nigerian economic growth. *European Journal of Business, Economics and Accountancy*, 4(4), 39-54.
- Vasani, S. A., Selvam, M. & Selvam, M. (2019). Relationship between real currency rate and economic growth in India. *Senith International Journal of Business Economics and Management Research*, 9(3), 19-35.
- Vo, D. H. & Shang, S. (2019). Currency rate volatility and disaggregated manufacturing exports: Evidence from an emerging country. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 12(1), 12-25.
- World Bank (2022). *Measuring Financial Inclusion: The Global Findex Database*. World Bank

- Yeni, N., Komara, A. T., Susanto, B. & Rusjiana, J. (2023). The effect of cost accounting information systems on operational cost control: Study at a consulting company in the city of Bandung. *Acman: Accounting and Management Journal*, 3(1), 28-34.
- Sulqarnain, M., Mustehsan, M., Balouch, U. K. & Munir, S. (2023). Assessing the influence of financial inclusion and digital finance on SMEs performance: The moderating role of technological adaptation. *Journal of Management Small and Medium Enterprises (SME's)*, 16(3), 459-476.